

Treatment of recycled cigarette butts (man-made pollutants) to prepare electrically conducting material

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Abstract : Recycling of waste is a major thrust area for decreasing environmental pollution. Disposed cigarette butts, a common waste material in our livelihood consisting of the cigarette filters, are toxic to aquatic life and degrade soil porosity. We report a simple process to prepare a conducting material by heat treatment of these used cigarette filters, which are composed largely of cellulose acetate. As they are non-biodegradable they therefore pose a serious threat to the environment after disposal. In keeping with the concept of recycled renewable resources, using the process of heat treatment (in Muffle furnace), we have prepared an active material from used cigarette filters. The pyrolyzed product is characterized by X-ray diffraction, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopic analysis, field emission scanning electron microscopy, ultra-violet visible spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering and zeta potential measurements. The electrical characteristics of the product have been measured to check its electrochemical behavior and results are found to be promising for further application as electronic materials.

Keywords : Renewable energy, cellulose acetate, cigarette butts, recycling, pyrolyzed products, current-voltage analysis.

Introduction

Global warming and limited resources of fossil fuels have been increasingly driving the world towards clean energy development. With the fast-growing market for portable electronic devices and hybrid electric vehicles, there has been an increasing and urgent demand for environment-friendly high-power energy resources. Low-cost and environment-friendly electri-

cally conductive systems are essential to meet the demand from modern society and emerging ecological concerns¹. Renewable energy has been considered as one of the strong contender to improve plight of people by the modern forms of energy². They find considerable interest in various applications such as electrical vehicles, micro sensors and portable electronics³⁻⁹. For such applications, it is important to develop an

advanced generation of electronic device that have the capability to supply high levels of power and energy¹⁰. Now a days supercapacitors, also known as electrochemical capacitors or ultra-capacitors, are gaining increasing attention because of their pulse power supply, long cycle life (> 100,000 cycles), simple working principle, and quick charge propagation¹¹⁻¹⁷.

Used cigarette filters are composed largely of cellulose acetate. They are disposable, non-biodegradable, toxic, and are a threat to the environment after usage. However, it has been reported that cellulose acetate can be directly utilized in the production of carbon materials containing meso-/micro-pore structures by only a carbonization process¹⁸. Cigarette butts, one of the most ubiquitous forms of garbage in the world, have been found to be toxic to saltwater and freshwater fish¹⁹⁻²¹. Emmons *et al.*²² indicated that the toxic chemical substances in one cigarette butt can kill half of the amount fish in 1 L of water every 96 h. Cigarette butts contain hazardous chemicals such as cadmium, arsenic and lead that are partially filtered out during smoking. However, when the butts are discarded, these chemicals leach into the environment, contaminating our waterways and land. According to one estimate, some 4.5 trillion cigarette butts from spent smokes make their way into the environment every year. Cigarette butts can take up to 12 months to break down in fresh water and up to 5 years to break down in seawater. Birds and aquatic animals can mistake the butts as food, resulting in serious digestive problems that may lead to death. Butts have been found in the stomach of young birds, sea turtles and other marine creatures. Another serious concern is that toxic chemicals such as lead and cadmium, which are trapped in the cigarette filter, can leach out in water. Within just one hour of contact with water, the chemicals begin to leach into the aquatic environment. One of the harmful effects of rampant disposal of cigarette filters is that it decreases soil porosity.

In the present day, various methods have been devised to develop clean technology from recycled materials. Our concept is to combine the virtues of recycling solid wastes and developing a one step process for the same. The present work focuses on recycling of the disposed cigarette filters, characterizing the pre-

pared materials and studying the electrochemical properties of the product. For a high-performance electronically conducting compound, electrode materials with a high surface area and proper pore size distribution are essential in utilizing a large amount of electrolyte ions with quick transfer mobility at the surface of the electrode material²³. It has been reported that the mesopores (2–50 nm) can provide desirable pathways for the movement of electrolyte ions^{24,25}, while the micropores (< 2 nm) further increase the surface area in order to enhance the electrical double-layer capacitance (EDLC). In our electrical property measurement of the pyrolyzed product we tried to understand the above mentioned fact. Lee *et al.*²⁶ has also developed a supercapacitor electrode from the same material. They highlighted mainly the electrical properties but in our work we discussed the characterization of the pyrolyzed product in detail. In this work the synthesized pyrolyzed material post synthesis is characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopic analysis, field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), ultra-violet visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering (DLS) and zeta potential measurements. Current-voltage (I-V) characteristics of the pyrolyzed sample are also measured to check its electrochemical activities.

Materials and methods :

Materials :

Used cigarette filters from Silk Cut (ITC Limited, India), Flake (ITC Limited, India) and Gold Flake (ITC Limited, India) were collected from the local shop garbage bin.

Preparation of pyrolyzed product :

A one step pyrolysis process is employed to obtain the active material from cigarette filters which are primarily composed of cellulose acetate. At the first step, the disposed off cigarette butts are collected and without any pretreatment the coated papers of the butts are carefully removed to obtain the filters. The filters are dried up in a dryer and then followed by the pyrolysis process in a muffle furnace at 900 °C for 2 h. A greyish white powdery pyrolyzed product is then cooled down to room temperature and collected. The sche-

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the work.

matic diagram of the research is presented in Fig. 1.

Material characterization :

Fourier transforms infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy :

The FTIR spectroscopic study was performed by using the Perkin-Elmer spectrum Express Version 1.03.00 instrument in the wave number range of 250 to 4500 cm^{-1} to confirm accordingly the groups in the pyrolyzed product.

Raman spectroscopy :

Raman spectroscopy is highly sensitive to the electronic structure and has proven to be an essential tool for the characterization of carbon based materials, especially for C=C double bonds which leads to high Raman intensities. Thus, it can also be a useful tool to characterize the pyrolyzed product. The Raman spectra was monitored using 1.96 eV (633 nm) line of a He-Ne laser in the HORIBA-JOBIN- YVON Lab RAM HR 800 instrument by placing the sample solution into a semi-micro stopper cuvette for an exposure time of 1 s.

X-Ray diffraction :

X-Ray diffraction analysis of the pyrolyzed product was performed at room temperature by X-PERT-PRO Pan analytical diffractometer using Cu K ($\lambda = 1.5406$ unit) as X-ray source at a generator voltage of

40 kV and current of 30 mA. The scanning rate was $1^\circ/\text{min}$.

FESEM analysis :

Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM from Zeiss Auriga instrument) was used at different magnifications to observe the surface morphology of pyrolyzed product. Prior to testing, the samples were coated with a thin layer of gold to avoid electrical charging during examination.

UV-Visible spectrometer :

The UV-Visible spectrometer was used to verify the formation of stable pyrolyzed product suspension. The absorbance at the characteristic peak exhibits in a linear relationship with concentration, following Beer's law, confirming the formation of a homogeneous solution. The experiment was done in an Agilent 8453 Spectrophotometer, USA in the wavelength region of 200 to 800 nm.

DLS study :

Zeta potential was measured to evaluate stability of the pyrolyzed product in an aqueous solution. The measurement was carried out in a dynamic light scattering instrument (Model : Zetasizer Nano-ZS90 System (Malvern Inc.)) to ascertain stability of the solution.

Electrical characterizations :

Current-voltage (I-V) characteristics of the pyrolyzed sample are measured in a conductivity cell of cell constant 0.1. The sample is dispersed in deionized (DI) water and measured by applying a DC bias in the range of -10 V to +10 V by employing a computer controlled source measuring unit (SMU) from Keithley 2611 B system Source Meter. The impedance, conductance and capacitance of pure DI water and pyrolyzed sample solution are measured by using an LCR meter.

Results and discussion*FTIR spectroscopy :*

The Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy deals with the stretching, bending and related wiggles responses of molecular species in a sample under test. As shown in Fig. 2a, the spectrum is correlated to the relevant molecular stretching and bending vibrations. The FTIR spectra of the pyrolyzed product is shown in Fig. 2a while Fig. 2b depicts the FTIR spectra of pure cellulose acetate. The peak observed in the pyrolyzed product at 3439 cm^{-1} may be due to O-H stretching which suggests the presence of a large number of hydroxyl groups, phenolic groups and alcoholic groups in the material backbone²⁷. The band at 2354 cm^{-1} is

due to the elongating vibration of aldehydes while the peak at 1107 cm^{-1} is identified due to the presence of aliphatic amine groups in the product. Also the band at 1638 cm^{-1} describes the peak of N-H bend for 1° amines. The absorbance band at 773 cm^{-1} ²⁸ may be due to the presence of alkyl halide in the pyrolyzed product. The different characteristic bands around $1500\text{--}2000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in Fig. 2b also indicate the existence of different oxygen functionalities in pure cellulose acetate material. The spectra shown in Fig. 2a and 2b are similar in nature though the slight shift in the peak position between the two figures is presumably due to the presence of interaction of the functional groups with the other products present in the pyrolyzed sample.

Raman spectroscopy :

Raman spectroscopy is an important method for the characterization of carbon-based materials where especially the conjugation of C-C double bond leads to high Raman intensities. As Raman scattering strongly depends on electronic structure of the materials, it can be a useful technique to characterize the pyrolyzed product. Fig. 3 shows the Raman spectra of the pyrolyzed material and the plot shows peaks at 141, 285, 396 and 643 cm^{-1} . From the plot, presence of strong Raman bands clearly indicate delocalization which exhibit potential for the material to be used for electrical purposes.

Fig. 2. (a) FTIR spectrum of the pyrolyzed product and (b) FTIR spectrum of pure cellulose acetate.

Fig. 3. Raman spectrum of the pyrolyzed product.

Fig. 4. XRD analysis of pyrolyzed product.

XRD analysis of the pyrolyzed product :

The X-ray diffraction pattern of the pyrolyzed product is shown in Fig. 4. X-Ray diffraction of the material shows different peaks at 24, 32, 37, 47, 54, 62 and 74°. The sharp peak located at around 25° and subsequent two peaks between 30~40 of 2θ for the pyrolyzed product samples signifies the incomplete graphitization by pyrolysis at a relatively low temperature of 900 °C (JCPDS No. 05-0667)²⁹. However, from the following XRD pattern there are strong diffraction of some other peaks, indicating the possibility of the presence of metal oxides like compounds. This is further confirmed from the peaks at 24 and 47° which indicate the presence of metal oxide in anatase phase^{30,31}.

FESEM :

Fig. 5a and 5b shows the FESEM images of the pyrolyzed product. It also shows that the pores are expanded within the material after the carbonization process. The surface morphology exhibits flake like structure with some extent of agglomeration.

UV-Visible spectrometer :

Fig. 6 shows the UV-Vis spectra of the pyrolyzed product which exhibits a hump at around 233 nm due to the π - π^* transition of C-C bond present in the pyrolyzed product. The homogeneous nature of the pyrolyzed solution was also confirmed from the absorbance

Fig. 5. (a, b) FESEM analysis of pyrolyzed product.

Fig. 6. UV spectroscopy analysis of pyrolyzed product.

value at λ_{\max} for different concentrations which exhibited compliance of Lambert-Beer's law.

DLS and zeta potential of the active material :

The zeta potential of pyrolyzed materials in an aqueous solution is measured in a dynamic light scattering instrument to study its stability as shown in Fig. 7. The product shows an average zeta potential value of -22.0 ± 6.80 mV, explaining the existence of a sufficient amount of negative charge density in the product.

Electrical characterization of the pyrolyzed product :

The comparative current-voltage (I-V) characteristics of the pyrolyzed sample solution and pure DI wa-

ter within a voltage range of -10 V to 10 V are plotted in Fig. 8, which suggest the current for pyrolyzed sample to be significantly higher than that in pure DI water. The variation of current with voltage for pure DI water is observed to be linear in nature, however, with the addition of 12 wt% of the pyrolyzed product in it, such nature changes to non-linear. Such a variation of the nature of current indicates a change of carrier transport properties due to the addition of pyrolyzed molecules in DI water. It is also apparent from comparative study that the current in the pyrolyzed sample solution for a particular voltage is much higher than in the pure DI water. The current flowing through pure DI water at 10 V is measured to be $176 \mu\text{A}$ whereas for the 12 wt% pyrolyzed sample solution it is measured to be 2.26 mA. Thus, the addition of 12 wt% of pyrolyzed sample in DI water increases its conductivity by at least one order.

The comparative variation of impedance, capacitance and conductance for pure DI water and the pyrolyzed sample solution within the frequency range of 50 Hz to 4 MHz is shown in Figs. 9(a), (b) and (c), respectively. It is apparent from Fig. 9(a) that the impedance of pure DI water and pyrolyzed sample solution remain almost constant up to 10 kHz and 100 kHz, respectively, and then decreases gradually with the increase of measuring frequency. However, the capacitance has been observed to decrease gradually with the increasing frequency as it is seen from Fig. 9(b). The variation of conductance with frequency for

Fig. 7. (a) Size distribution by intensity analysis of the pyrolysed product and (b) Zeta potential distribution analysis of the pyrolyzed product.

Fig. 8. Comparative plots of current-voltage (I-V) characteristics of pure DI water and the solution with pyrolyzed sample.

the pure DI water and pyrolyzed sample solution is plotted in Fig. 9(c) which shows that the conductance remains almost constant in the frequency range considered.

In comparison to pure DI water, the conductance of pyrolyzed sample solution is observed to be higher. At 1 kHz, the value of conductance for pure DI water is measured to be $9.9 \mu\text{S}$ whereas for 12 wt% pyrolyzed sample solution it is measured to be $139 \mu\text{S}$. Hence, the difference in magnitude of the overall conductance of the pyrolyzed solution with respect to the pure DI water solution is considered to be the effect of dispersion of pyrolyzed sample solution which also corroborates the observation from the comparative

Fig. 9. Comparative plots of the variation of : (a) Impedance, (b) Capacitance and (c) Conductance with frequency for pure DI water and pyrolyzed sample solution.

I-V plots and Raman studies.

Conclusion

The pyrolyzed material that we have synthesized is a good conductive material which can be further used in different electronics field and also aims to reduce environmental pollution caused by used cigarette filters. Different types of characterization like XRD, FTIR, Raman, UV and DLS study have lead to the formation of new promising material from the man-made pollutant. As no pretreatment is required on the used cigarette filters before the carbonization process, this is also cost effective as it involves no fabrication procedure. Current-voltage curve of the material indicates a significant rise in conductivity which property indicates the use of the material in electronic application in future.

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